

IMPLEMENTING AUTHENTIC MATERIALS IN TEACHING READING COMPREHENSION OF EFL LEARNERS

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Annotation: The aim of this study was to investigate the effect of authentic-based and non-authentic-based materials on improving reading comprehension of the Uzbek intermediate EFL learners. The data analysis and the results of this research revealed authentic group acted noticeably on the improvement of reading comprehension of the learners.

Keywords: Authentic-Based Materials, Non-Authentic-Based Materials, Reading Comprehension.

In Uzbek educational system, the EFL learners' reading achievements are relatively poor. The learners have many problems in understanding the meaning some words in the text that they do not understand the meaning of the text. For that reason, they become demotivated to read an English text. According to the problem, the study is going to focus on the importance of authentic materials on the Uzbek EFL learners' reading achievements. As the scientist Mousavi told, over the past three decades, authentic-based materials were used in EFL classes as a result of the spread of the communicative approach.

Martinez defines authentic-based materials as the materials which are prepared for native speakers and not designed to be used for teaching purposes. Nuttall commented that authentic-based materials can be motivating because they are proof that the language is used for real-life purpose by real people. The difference is not in the language materials themselves but rather on their outcomes and their effectiveness. In this regard, “it has been traditionally supposed that the language presented to learners should be simplified in some way for easy access and acquisition, nowadays there are recommendations that the language presented should be authentic”. In contrast, Miller state that non-authentic materials are those materials that are specially designed for learning purpose and the language used in them is artificial with well- formed sentence all the time which is useful for teaching grammar. Course book, textbook, and student work sheets are good instances of non-authentic materials.

Many studies have focused on the authentic-based materials and their effects on different parts of English language which some of them are mentioned in the next section but to the best researcher's knowledge, no research studies have been worked

on the comparison of authentic-based materials and non-authentic-based materials on reading comprehension. To fill the gap, the present study was going to explore the effect of authentic-based materials versus non-authentic-based materials on the Uzbek intermediate EFL learners' reading comprehension performance.

Reading skill may be significant in our country where English is taught as a foreign language because our students need this skill to continue in their academic education. This important skill can be improved by the use of authentic-based and non-authentic-based materials but it is not clear which one of the materials will be more effective in developing reading comprehension. For that reason, the present study tried to reveal the effectiveness of authentic materials in comparison of non-authentic materials in improving reading comprehension performance.

Most of reading materials in Uzbek educational system are non-authentic-based materials which are designed for educational purposes (e.g., English course books for secondary schools and high schools). Possibly, it may prevent most of the EFL learners to be able to use the language communicatively. In order to overcome the problem, the researcher tried to disclose the advantages of authentic-based materials in improving the EFL learners to use language communicatively. EFL Learners often have difficulties learning English without appropriate learning materials. In practice, reading texts are designed either too difficult or too easy for the learners. Without appropriate reading texts that suit the learners, language learners cannot improve their performance in reading skill. Appropriate reading texts refer to those reading texts which are compatible with students' language proficiency.

The role of reading comprehension ability has long been neglected, but currently, it is again receiving attention in the language teaching curriculum. Reading has been the focus of varied and versatile research, e.g., the acquisition of vocabulary in terms of frequency and saliency reading processes, strategies, the nature of reading difficulties and abilities in second language learning. Skimming is defined as to look at a text or a chapter quickly in order to get a general opinion on the contents. It requires a greater degree of reading and word recognition skills as it includes a more thorough understanding of the text.

Considering the results obtained from the analysis of the related data, it can be argued that the authentic-based materials used in teaching reading in our setting were effective in the authentic group. The authentic reading comprehension passages were interesting for the language learners. After reading authentic texts, students became more motivated to read about their own favorite topics and new things. Social reasons for reading, is another domain of motivation which had an increase. It affirms the fact that readers not only read the texts for themselves, but also have motivation to deliver the new information they got from the texts to other people. Here, the focus of reading is on the content in which readers make an interaction with the text, and not

on the linguistic features of the text. Last but not least, language learners worked in groups in the authentic group through, sharing opinions could perform effectively in reading comprehending.

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